

Resource Efficiency

in technical terms

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Material resources outlook

OECD, Global Material Resources Outlook to 2060: Economic Drivers and Environmental Consequences. 2019

Global wood cycle from harvesting to waste treatment including recycling

In Million oven-dry metric tonnes, reference year 2021

Yayla et al. (2025) Nat Sustain 8, 1013–1025

Global log-wood use

Obvious differences

Tobias Nenning

What will be „the“ future wood species?

Conifers:

- AB → *Abies alba*
- AG → *Abies grandis*
- LD → *Larix decidua*
- PI → *Picea abies*
- PC → *Pinus cembra*
- PY → *Pinus sylvestris*
- PS → *Pinus strobus*
- PM → *Pseudotsuga menziesii*
- TB → *Taxus baccata*

Deciduous wood:

- AP → *Acer pseudoplatanus*
- AA → *Ailanthus altissima*
- AG → *Alnus glutinosa*
- BS → *Betula spp.*
- CB → *Carpinus betulus*
- CS → *Castanea sativa*
- CA → *Corylus avellane*
- FS → *Fagus sylvatica*
- FE → *Fraxinus excelsior*
- JR → *Juglans regia*
- PO → *Populus spp.*
- PA → *Prunus avium*
- PR → *Pyrus spp.*
- PT → *Paulownia tomentosa*
- QU → *Quercus spp.*
- QR → *Quercus rubra*
- RP → *Robinia pseudoacacia*
- SA → *Salix spp.*
- ST → *Sorbus torminalis*
- TS → *Tilia spp.*
- US → *Ulmus spp.*

Huber et al (2023)

Solid wood processing

€€€ - added value

Yield

Primary processing technologies

Pramreiter et al. (2023)

Comparison of production process

General considerations

Solid Wood → Engineered Wood Products → Wood-based panels

Homogenization, characteristic strength, yield, adhesive, density, energy, carbon footprint, process cost...

Average strength, modulus, required wood quality, ...

Performance comparison

Bliem, Konnerth (2021)
 Jakob et al (2022) The Strength and
 Stiffness of Oriented Wood and
 Cellulose-Fibre Materials: A Review.
 Progress of Material Science

Yield & performance

Pramreiter et al 2022

Life-cycle Parameters

- **Primary energy demand**
- **Carbon storage potential**
- **Global warming potential (GWP)**
- ...

Specific total **primary energy demand**

Pramreiter et al (2024) Engineered Wood Products (EWP) – Resource Efficiency and Environmental Performance

Hardwood for structural products

Beech

Oak

Poplar

3-D Trees: Point Clouds (A. Tockner)

Branch

Strong Hardwood: Better Understanding of Properties x Performance x Process

Nenning et al.

Stem

UniStrand: Structural Strand Based Products

Hardwood in construction: Strip-like laminations

A. Neumüller & S. Lux

Understanding potential of branch wood

Wood quality

Structure

Properties

Mechanical branch wood properties²

Processing

The Macrofiber Technology³

WOOD KPLUS

Performance

1: Tockner A., Institute of Forest Growth, 2: Nenning et al. (2024), 3: Bliem et al. (2020)

Nenning et al 2025

CLT analogue based on strands: UniStrand

Strength classes

Stress distribution in wall element

optimized USB composite panel

Multi-story building application

Material comparison

Strength graded
solid wood

Unidirectional Strand Board
USB

Oriented Strand Board
OSB

Mechanical performance of single layers

A. Fasalek & L. Malzl

Hardwood GLT – concept of strip-like laminations

Homogenization instead of grading & defect elimination

Dynamic modulus of single laminations

What is needed?

- New processing concepts:
 - new mass timber products & processes for low quality wood & hardwood as alternative to energetic use with high added value
- Combinations of processes vs. linear thinking
- Dematerialization of mass timber materials
- Re-use, recycling concepts (EU circularity rate currently 10%)

- Reduce energy demand in production (bark)
- Low carbon footprint building materials
- Adhesives – biobased, low carbon footprint

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